

RANI RASMANI: AS A SOCIAL EDUCATOR

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ABSTRACT:

Rani Rasmani is a unique noble woman of 19th century Bengal. She provided an ecosystem for new thinking (Pattanaik, 2021). This was a Qualitative Approach. The main objectives of this study were to study the contribution of Rani Rasmani as a social educator and to study the relevance of her ideas in this context in the present situation.

The methodology of research was Historical method and the sources examined were the primary and secondary sources, documentary analysis were used. To study led to the following conclusions that as a social educator, she led by example, demonstrating the importance of social responsibility, compassion, and community service; aiming to eliminate caste-based discrimination and promote universal brotherhood; she is such a personality and social educator to all people and especially to women.

KEYWORDS:

RANI RASMANI, SOCIAL EDUCATOR.

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INTRODUCTION

Education' is one of the most important and essential aspects of human life in 21st century. The only thing that depends on the development of student as well as society is education. Social educators conduct social-educational activities aimed at people suffering from various problems that help them reintegrate into the mainstream of society. Any ideal person can be a social teacher if she has the ideals of social education and values in him.

Rani Rasmani is such a remarkable personality. She played a key role in changing society in Bengal forever and she started the first anti-British movement in Bengal. She was able to generate a vast amount of wealth that she used shrewdly for various philanthropic, political and religious projects (Pattanaik, 2021). Rani Rasmani did not expect any benefit from the people in return for her services. The noble deeds of this noble woman have made her memorable to the masses.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The present study is entitled as "Rani Rasmani: As a Social Educator."

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF KEY TERMS

The researcher has highlighted the necessity to define some concepts operationally. These are:

- **SOCIAL EDUCATOR**

Researchers have studied that social learning is

the experience that helps improve the individual's ability to participate in group life and enables the individual to lead a normal life through adaptation to society. It is possible through an ideal person who has this experience and one such person is Rani Rasmani. Her social learning activities are analyzed in this study.

- **RANI RASMANI**

She was born on 24 September, 1793AD, in the village Kona of Halisahar, in the District of North twenty four Parganas, West Bengal, India. She was a social educationist, philanthropist, social reformer in the 19th century.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What were the contributions of Rani Rasmani as a social educator?
2. What is the relevance of Rani Rasmani's ideas in this context in the present situation?

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the present study are:

1. To study the contribution of Rani Rasmani as a social educator.
2. To study the relevance of Rani Rasmani's ideas in this context in the present situation.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study was delimited to Rani Rasmani's contribution as a social educator in India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study that is being conducted is on "**Rani Rasmani: As a Social Educator**" a qualitative analysis. It is the Historical Research.

SOURCES OF DATA

In the present study a documentary analysis has been taken by the primary sources and secondary sources. The researcher has used Stone Inscriptions, various Govt. Documents etc. as secondary sources. The researcher has used research papers, magazines, newspapers etc. as secondary sources.

CRITICISM OF DATA

There are two types of historical criticism like external and internal criticism. External criticism is aimed at establishing the authenticity or genuineness of the data. In the present study the external and internal criticism are used. Most of the works of Rani Rasmani were examined critically. The present research is an attempt to assess the contributions of a social reformer in the field of education and social up liftment.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Rani Rasmani is a benevolent form of divine power, full of self-reliance, rich in human values, and inspired by the spirit of God. Therefore, in the dark social environment of 19th century India, an almost illiterate woman born in a poor family, with her intelligence, talent and ingenuity repeatedly attacked the English rulers and earned their respect and loyalty. The tyrannical landlord class, lowly Brahmin society, English imperialism, and the compassionate she sometimes stood by the side of the downtrend people and women, sometimes did various philanthropic activities for the benefit of the people.

In that era, there was not much opportunity for girls' education, schools and colleges were not developed as much as today. Girls did not have much opportunity to go out of the house, so she did not get any opportunity for traditional education. She learned to read and write at home from her father and learned the work of a house girl from her mother. The ideals of respect for elders that she received from her parents from childhood, she kept intact throughout her life.

The purpose of her life practice was to fulfil the welfare of family, society and above all mankind through selfless work. She constructed Dakshineswar Temple and various Ghats like Antarjali Ghat for Ganges pilgrims, a private bank for economic development, Hindu schools for the spread of education, medical colleges for good treatment of poor people were built in the bosom of unfortunate Bengal. This zamindar family of Janbazar spent a lot of money per person for the overall development of the society.

The study enables people to assess the cultural reformation attempted through her social education. Her approach to formal as well as non-formal education is relevant to the modern world. Her reforms and contributions were:

Recognizing education as a tool for social mobility and change, she undertook the education of disadvantaged poor students with a focus on holistic education. She also helped various educational institutions.

Inter-caste marriages have been encouraged as a means of promoting social harmony by breaking down caste barriers. She advocated ahimsa (non-violence) and believed in peaceful methods of protest and reform.

She addressed issues like child marriage, sati, and women's property rights. Collaborated with prominent social reformers of her time, such as Raja Rammohan Roy, Ishwarchandra Vidyasagar, etc. who expanded the reform efforts; and her life and reforms are emblematic of the larger social reform movement in India today. Her emphasis on egalitarianism, unity and social justice is relevant and serves as an ideal for contemporary society. (Samanta, 2018)

Even though she herself was a widow, she also established the temple in the caste-bound society of that time. She advocated and facilitated the entry of lower castes into temples, challenging orthodox Brahminical hegemony and caste-based restrictions. She consecrated temples where people of all castes could worship.

By adopting a holistic approach to education, her social education initiatives aimed to create a more just, equitable, and compassionate society, empowering individuals to become active agents of change. Her legacy continues to inspire social educators and community development initiatives in India and beyond.

Her life philosophy also reflects her role as a social educator and believed in the power of education to transform students and society, and her work reflects this commitment. Also, she was a pioneering social educator who went beyond traditional teaching methods to empower all students, women and communities. The researcher has studied aspects of her life philosophy that highlight her role as a social educator like:

- **CRITICAL THINKING**

She encouraged individuals to think critically and question the status quo.

- **INCLUSIVITY**

Lokmata Rani Rashmoni was a very reverent and spiritual woman who founded the temple of Dakshineswar on the banks of the river Ganges in North 24 Parganas, west Bengal, India (Ghosh, 1988). She advocated for inclusive education, reaching out to marginalized communities and promoting social cohesion and economic growth.

- **KNOWLEDGE**

She believed in the importance of knowledge and education for personal growth and development.

- **LIFELONG LEARNING**

She believed in the importance of lifelong learning, encouraging individuals to acquire new skills and knowledge in continuous learning throughout their lives.

- **WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH EDUCATION**

She believed that education was the key to empowering individuals, especially women, to take control of their lives. She provided education and vocational training to women, enabling them to assert their rights, become economically independent, and challenge patriarchal norms.

- **SOCIAL INJUSTICES**

She used her platform to raise awareness about social injustices, mobilizing support for causes like education, healthcare, and women's empowerment.

- **EDUCATION FOR SOCIAL CHANGE**

She saw education as a means to bring about social change, addressing issues like poverty, inequality, and discrimination.

- **CHALLENGED SOCIAL NORMS**

She questioned societal norms that perpetuated gender inequality, caste system, and religious discrimination, encouraging critical thinking and inquiry; through her schools and philanthropic work, advocated for social reform, addressing issues like child marriage, sati, and women's property rights. (Das, 1425b).

Besides, all the qualities that were present in him were compassion, charity, kindness, responsibility, accountability, dutiful or devotion to duty, forgiveness, tolerance, courtesy, sympathy and faithfulness etc.

Through her social education initiatives, she aimed to create a more just, equitable, and compassionate society, empowering individuals to become active agents of change. Her legacy continues to inspire social education and community development initiatives in India.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The present study is to reveal the social work for the upliftment of the depressed classes by Rani Rasmani. As the patriot of the upper castes, the British, who has made a place in history as the creator of women's freedom, the country's welfare. The scope of his activities was great. She was born to protect women and society from all these social prejudices and social degradation and she dedicated her life for the welfare of all beings. From her philosophy of life the students get the education of humanity. All these things show that she wanted to get rid of the prejudices of the society by joining the social movement.

Also, she provided aid and support during natural disasters and calamities. She educated women on their rights, health, and economic independence. She promoted health awareness programs. She advocated for the rights of marginalized communities, including Dalits and widows. She encouraged community participation in development initiatives. She promoted environmental conservation and

sustainability. She preserved and promoted Indian cultural heritage, including art, literature, and music. (Roy, 1990)

It is very essential to understand her ideas of education since they are largely based on deep concern for humanity. The purpose of education, according to him is to cultivate the right relationships, not only between individuals, but also between the individual and society. The findings and conclusions of the study are her life philosophy and work as a social educator have inspired generations to value education as a powerful tool for personal and social transformation.

"Rani Rasmani - A name that has been engraved in golden scripts in the pages of history, Rani Rasmani - a name delivering welfare, Rani Rasmani - a name radiant like a sun, Rani Rasmani - a name full of nectar mingled with the relatedness of motherhood, Rani Rasmani- a name self-evident and being in harmony with her prowess, spirituality, honesty and magnanimity" (Ray, 1990, p. 2). That is, she did not just come out of the inner world and work with the man, she decided on the fearlessness of the man by mastering all the bravery and brilliance of the man, and while doing the work, no feminine weakness was seen in her character.

She brought about a silent revolution to redeem the downtrodden people of Bengal. Education was interpreted by him to mean the complete development of man through the successive stages of life and the preparation for life. She was a noted spiritual leader, social reformer and philosopher from west Bengal, India. She also played a unique role as a social educator. Her contributions ranged in the fields of spirituality, socio-political reforms and education, aiming to eliminate caste-based discrimination and promote universal brotherhood. As a social educator, she led by example, demonstrating the importance of social responsibility, compassion, and community service. She has taught the use of money through his various philanthropic works and she set an example in the history of Bengal for helping the helpless people.

Her values, philanthropic activities and her sense of humanity towards the public make her a role model for the entire society especially students to emulate and she is regarded as a social teacher all over the world. The researcher has concluded that Rani Rasmani is such a personality and above all a social educator who is not only a social educator to students but also a social educator to all common people and especially to women.

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